

First Newsletter is Out!

Dear Reader,

SiCOMB is a European project that is developing an innovative chip-based optical frequency comb. Find below what we have been up to this year!

Save the date for SiCOMB next WEBINAR!

SiCOMB is delighted to invite you to its next **online seminar**: "Exploring the innovations behind the methodology of the SiCOMB Project", which will take place on March 15th at 15.30 CEST.

[Sign up for this exciting event!](#)

For this session, three of SiCOMB's researchers will give you an insight on contribution to this project, the innovations in their researches and what it means for groundbreaking applications. Find below the outline for this exciting event.

From initial materials findings to the future ground-breaking applications

Speaker: **Mikael Syväjärvi**

Radical new technologies are based on experiences in materials growth that builds competence to address challenges in the emerging technology concepts. The presentation shares experiences creating new avenues for European research and innovation in SiC and the technology related to sustainable goals.

Low temperature ($T < 800^{\circ}\text{C}$) deposition of SiC thin films by activated processes (PECVD, PVD, HWCVD)

Speaker: **Didier Chaussende**

The presentation will introduce the main approaches to deposit SiC thin films at low temperatures. For kinetic reasons, the processes must be activated by plasma or hot filament. This process allows to deposit down to room temperature, i.e. on thermally sensitive substrates. The link between deposition conditions and film properties will be discussed.

Introduction to Chemical Vapor Deposition of 3C-SiC on Si at T=800 to 1200°C compatible to Si-CMOS Technology

Speaker: **Peter Wellmann**

The presentation will briefly introduce the chemical vapor deposition of cubic SiC on Si-wafer using the gas precursors silane and propane. Besides the experimental setup, issues of seeding of 3C-SiC on Si as well as challenges of the layer deposition process will be discussed.

Advancements in the next CVD reactor and establishments of the CMP Process

The layers required for the frequency comb function are non-standard. The work package in materials growth has explored novel approaches to SiC growth. The work has also initiated the industrial collaboration. Lowering growth temperatures revealed new process regimes.

Cubic silicon carbide (3C-SiC) thin films are usually deposited hetero-epitaxially on silicon wafers using chemical vapor deposition (CVD) at 1300°C to 1350°C. To ensure compatibility with silicon-based metal-oxide-semiconductor (MOS) device processing, it is necessary to lower the growth temperature to a temperature range between 800°C - 1200°C.

For this purpose, the sufficient supply of the standard CVD precursors silane (SiH_4) and propane (C_3H_8) requires a new calibration of the gas fluxes and an adaption of the so-called silicon to carbon ratio in front of the growth interface. The first results of the growth process study in the temperature regime between 1100°C and 1200°C have been presented during the international conference on silicon carbide and related materials (ECSCRM2021) in Tours (France) in October 2021. As one significant result, a process regime was presented with exhibits a significant reduction of unintentional particle deposition on the epitaxial 3C-SiC films*.

Image: PVD reactor made by Plassys Bestek and used to deposit SiC thin layer at low temperature

To achieve even lower deposition temperature (typically lower than 800°C), different approaches are explored, such as plasma-enhanced chemical vapor deposition (in collaboration with Plasma-Therm Europe), physical vapour deposition (PVD) and hot filament chemical vapor deposition (HFCVD). These different deposition processes allow getting SiC thin films with an extensive range of chemical, structural, and optical properties. By adjusting the layer composition - Si_xC_y with or without hydrogen-its crystallinity -from amorphous to crystalline layers-both the refractive index and the attenuation coefficient can be customized to meet the photonic device specifications. This development is supported by the state of the art characterization tools, probing the films down to the nanometer scale**.

*Proceedings of the ECSCRM 2021 meeting: submitted to Materials Science Forum (TransTech.Publ.)

**Tuning the Optical Properties of PVD Deposited SiC Coatings by a Design of Experiments Approach, by V.Tabouret et al. to be presented at ICMCTF 2022 in San Diego, USA.

When Politecnico di Torino meets DTU: Exchanges on respective advancement on wide bandgap semiconductors: GaN, SiC, and Lithium Niobate

Technical University of Denmark (DTU) has prepared the first microring test structures towards frequency comb. Politecnico di Torino (PoliTo) will integrate these with temperature controllers.

Temperature controllers are needed since temperature variations cause drift in the device. The drift causes a shift in frequency lines, and the shift causes inaccuracy of performance since laser and microring resonance will misalign due to the self-heating.

The drift can be from several sources, such as the generation of heat due to waveguide loss. Such self-generated heat is difficult to control, and the generated heat also depends on input power level. A temperature controller can be used to keep the device temperature stable and thereby have a stable operation.

A frequency comb development includes various considerations in practical manufacturing steps. The first consideration is to have relevant material properties to tightly confine the light in the silicon carbide. There is no commercial silicon carbide directly applicable for the frequency comb purpose since the layer with the necessary properties should be on the insulator. During the first project year, the materials partners FAU and CNRS have made their initial development work to fabricate material stacks with needed properties.

The work includes fabrication of material as well as preparation of the surfaces. First material samples have become available for device development.

The primary step in device development is microring fabrication. Such samples with microrings were delivered by DTU to PoliTo at a visit in September 2021. The microring is an essential feature since it enhances nonlinear processing such as four-wave mixing. The processing results in conversion of the laser light to other wavelengths, which is the basis for frequency comb generation. The microring resonator structure includes coupling features like edge coupler, grating coupling, etc.

To understand details in the properties and geometries of the samples, PoliTo visited DTU to discuss details of measurements and selection of lasers. The pandemic situation challenged the interactive collaboration and visits, but both visits could be managed during the autumn of 2021. Exchange visits are helpful both as part of project exchange and also for the future on other materials research and innovation. The visits included discussions on respective advancements on wide bandgap semiconductors: gallium nitride, silicon carbide polytypes, and lithium niobate.

Developing an actual test structure demonstrated a critical step in the project where partners can start to align their experimental efforts after their development work during the first phase of the SiComb project. At the end of March, the project will meet several deliverables.

Report on optimized design and processing for low-loss and dispersion controllable SiC waveguides

At DTU, we are focusing on simulating the optical devices, developing the nanofabrication processes, and characterizing the performance of the devices. Low waveguide loss is one of the most important properties for frequency comb generation. The loss is usually caused by the material and the later fabrication imperfection. To measure the loss induced by the material, we built a prism coupler setup. Generally, it consists of a laser source, a prism to couple the light into the amorphous (a-)SiC thin film, and a mobile detector to measure the light intensity along the light path. Before this prism coupler setup, the loss is extracted after the device fabrication and characterization, which is jointly contributed by both material absorption and nanofabrication imperfection. Using this setup, we measured the PECVD deposited a-SiC-on-insulator wafers provided by CNRS, and extracted the thin-film loss, which is 6 dB/cm. This setup enables the separation of material loss and fabrication loss, thus facilitating the optimization direction for material and fabrication. Based on the PECVD deposited a-SiC samples, we optimized nanofabrication processes, including high-resolution E-beam lithography and high-aspect-ratio ICP-RIE dry etching. We developed two process flows. One used e-beam resist directly as a mask, and the etching uses SF₆ and O₂. This process had a controllable etching rate and high selectivity. Still, the redeposition induced strong light scattering resulted in a high light propagation loss of the a-SiC waveguide, which was 16 dB/cm. The other used metal as a hard mask, and the etching uses SF₆ only. This process had an ultrafast etching rate but with a smooth sidewall, and the loss of the a-SiC waveguide is largely reduced to 9 dB/cm. For total loss of 9 dB/cm, 6 dB/cm is from the material loss and the extra 3 dB/cm loss is caused by the fabrication imperfection. Hence, the fabrication process can be further optimized to reduce the loss below 3 dB/cm.

Photograph of prism coupler setup with a 4" SiCOI wafer under measurement

Scanning electron microscope 5SEM^o image of microring resonators coupled by grating couplers

We also designed and characterized grating couplers, and microring resonators based on the PECVD deposited a-SiC samples. Low-loss grating couplers are used to efficiently couple the light between the optical fibers and the waveguides. Both uniform and apodized gratings were designed. By carefully tailoring the parameters to make the grating diffractive profile match the mode in the fiber, a grating coupler with high efficiency of 50% was obtained during the simulation. The microring resonators with anomalous and near-zero group velocity dispersion were designed by optimizing the waveguides' dimension and curvature, which is essential for the frequency comb generation. Under the current material and fabrication processes, we could acquire a-SiC microring resonators with a high-quality factor of 6×10^4 .

In conclusion, we are designing, fabricating and characterizing a-SiC waveguides by continuous optimization for efficient frequency comb generation.

SiCOMB under the spotlight: where you could find us this year

Over the last year, SiCOMB has participated in several events to expand its network and visibility, raising awareness of its innovation among the scientific community and the general public.

In September 2021, the project took part in the 47th edition of the Micro and Nano Engineering Conference (Torino, September 20th-23th). It represented for micro-/nano- engineers and scientists an important showcase for the technology advancement achieved over the last two years, and SiCOMB actively participated in the conference, with the contribution of the Project Coordinator Dr. Haiyan Ou: Associate Professor at the Technical University of Denmark, she presented a talk on how Nano-engineering unlocks the potential of SiC for Photonic.

Another significant event was the European Innovation Council Summit 2021 (Brussels, November 24th-25th, 2021). SiCOMB is indeed part of the EIC eco-system partners (as project financed by the H2020 FET-Open, which is now - with Horizon Europe - the EIC Pathfinder programme). The event gathered start-ups, SMEs, innovators, researchers, corporates, and potential investors from all around the world, encouraging connections and providing sessions on major policy updates as well as on achievements and challenges to be faced as far as technology and innovation in Europe is concerned.

Last but not least, SiCOMB shared its findings through the webinar "Silicone Carbide outside electronic applications", in December 14th, 2021. The event was arranged jointly with another project working with SiC material: SiC Nano for Picogeo. The overall purpose was to investigate the new challenging applications of this innovative and not yet fully explored material. SiCOMB held the second part of the seminar, through the presentation of Dr. Haiyan Ou, followed by Prof. Peter Wellman from the project partner university FAU. Both contributions were aimed at illustrating the unique properties of SiC unlocked by leveraging the advances of nanofabrication and high-quality material.

To conclude, a further critical element for the project is the high participation of young researchers, who contribute to SiCOMB's objectives and outcomes with their research, activities, and competences. Among them: Xiaodong Shi -Research Assistant at the Technical University of Denmark - collaborated to several project related articles; post-doctoral researcher Valentina Bertana, from Politecnico di Torino, is designing a proper system that aims to stabilize the working conditions of the SiC devices. Finally, FAU Doctorate Steiner Johanesse collaborates with SiCOMB through its publications and competences related to SiC, crystal growth and numerical simulations. Also, SiCOMB partner Mellanox is planning to take on board four young researchers during 2022, while CNRS just involved in the project the post-doctoral research Vincent Tabouret and its work on Chemical Vapor Deposition (CVD) furnaces. More info about their career in our section Meet our researchers.

Meet Our Researchers

Xiaodong Shi

Field of Expertise : Integrated photonics,
nonlinear optics, nanofabrication
University: Technical University of
Denmark

"Hopefully, our work can pave the way and inspire future work for SiC integrated photonics."

I am currently pursuing a Post Doctorate at DTU Fotonik, working on silicon carbide (SiC) integrated photonics. Nanofabrication is one of my daily works that various photonic devices with hundreds of nanometer dimensions are patterned in a small chip through a series of processing. Developing nanofabrication processes for new materials or platforms can often encounter unexpected problems, which may need to spend plenty of time to solve. It took almost two years to develop and optimize the fabrication processes of making the SiC-on-insulator photonic integrated platform and SiC nanodevices. These processes are very robust, thus, can benefit all the SiC applications that require SiC nanofabrication, such as photonic integrated circuits (PIC). It is a great pleasure for me to be involved in the Horizon 2020 FET Open project, SiComb. We explore the optical properties of different polytypes of SiC, which are grown or deposited through various methods. We are trying to fabricate low-loss SiC microring resonators and achieve frequency comb generation in SiC integrated platforms, which can be used as on-chip wavelength division multiplexing light sources for large-scale SiC PIC. Hopefully, our work can pave the way and inspire future work for SiC integrated photonics.

Valentina Bertana

Field of Expertise : Additive
Manufacturing and integrated systems
University: Politecnico di Torino

**“From the SiComb project, I’m
looking forward to discovering
new applications that are strictly
related to nanotechnologies”**

One of the most exciting aspects of my work is that I can often face various research topics and meet new people. I also enjoy of making new discoveries with my colleagues which is something difficult to find in other types of jobs. I love working in a team; sharing victories and failures can create strong bonds. If we add to it kindness and patience, one can obtain the recipe of the best working group! This is crucial since it is not always sunshine and rainbows, particularly in the basic research. I clearly remember when, during a project, the more we worked hard on it, the more the results did no come. This would have been a lot more frustrating if I had to face all those issues myself. From the SiComb project, I’m looking forward to discovering new applications strictly related to nanotechnologies: during my PhD, I also worked with two-photon polymerization, and the possibility to precisely define structures at such a tiny scale is absolutely fascinating. Another thing even more fascinating is trying to interface this tiny word with our macroscopic one. In the next 10 years, I hope one of the research projects I am carrying on inside my group will turn into a ground-breaking application that will significantly enhance people’s lives.

Manuel Kollmuß

Field of Expertise : Vapor phase growth
of SiC

University: Friedrich-Alexander-
Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg

**"I hope that SiC can overcome its
still present limitations and
become a widely used material in
electrical and optical applications."**

Currently I am doing my PhD at the FAU Erlangen-Nürnberg on the growth of cubic silicon carbide. I have been involved in the SiComb project since the beginning. Besides the growth of thin cubic silicon carbide films on silicon at low temperatures using CVD, I am developing a process to transfer the silicon carbide layers to a different substrate. This is necessary to reduce optical losses in the optical devices built on the silicon carbide layers. One of the most fascinating aspects of my work is that you are faced with new challenges every day. But often, it can be challenging to find solutions for these problems entirely on your own. Therefore, discussing with your colleagues and project partners to find possible solutions together is something I highly enjoy in this project. I am looking forward to continuing this nice collaboration for project implementation and hopefully beyond. For the future of our research topic, I hope that cubic silicon carbide can overcome its still present limitations and become a widely used material in electrical and optical applications.

Dana Winkowski and Yuval Dori

Field of Expertise: Electrical Engineering, in the field of computer hardware, electrical devices and communications.

University: Tel Aviv University

“We will be excited and honoured to see that most data centres worldwide are using our company's optical communication solution”

- What do you find most fascinating about your work?

We are excited to be a part of an advanced research group that explores the most cutting edge optical communication solutions.

- What are you looking forward to in this new research project?

Our goal in this project is to provide simple, straightforward, and incisive conclusions regarding the system design that will contribute to the company.

- What would you like to see happening within your field in the next 10 years?

We will be excited and honoured to see that most data centres worldwide are using our company's optical communication solution, in addition to deep research that will lead to further technological developments.

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